

Screening of Metal Complexes for Biological Activity. Part—IV : Synthesis of Pharmacologically and Microbiologically Active Thiocyanato and Oxalato Complexes of Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} with 3-Phenylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2

S. K. BAJPAI

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

and

G. N. SHUKLA

Chemistry Department, Sri Jai Narain Degree College, Lucknow

Manuscript received 9 July 1981, accepted 10 December 1981

Complexes of formula $(MX_2L)_2$ where $M=Fe^{2+}$, Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ; $X=0.5$ $C_2O_4^{2-}$ or SCN^- and $L=3$ -phenylaminomethyl benzoxazolinone-2, have been prepared and characterised on the basis of analysis, conductance, magnetic moment, ir and diffuse reflectance spectral data. All the complexes were subjected to various pharmacological tests viz., toxicity, effect on CNS and CVS, antiinflammatory activity, antianaphylactic activity and diuresis. Complexes were also screened against *E. histolytica* and *S. aureus* to evaluate their amoebicidal and bactericidal actions respectively. Fungitoxicity was studied against *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *F. solani*. Toxicity, anti-amoebic, anti-bacterial and antifungal activities are inversely proportional to the radius of metal ion.

IN continuation of previous work on synthesis of transition metal complexes with a view to evaluate their analytical¹⁻³ and pharmacological⁴⁻⁶ significance we report here the coordination complexes of bivalent iron, cobalt, nickel and copper with 3-phenylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2. The complexes have been characterised on the basis of their analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurement, electronic and infrared spectral data. All the complexes have been subjected to various pharmacological tests viz., toxicity, effect on central nervous system (CNS), cardiovascular system (CVS), diuresis (DU), antiinflammatory activity (AIA) and anti passive cutaneous anaphylaxis (PCA). In addition, amoebicidal, bactericidal and fungicidal activities of these complexes have also been evaluated.

Experimental

(a) *Chemical methods*: Iron(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II) salts and ammonium thiocyanate used were of BDH AR grade or equivalent quality. Ligand 3-phenylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2 (PAB) was prepared by the method of Varma and Nobles⁷.

Oxalate complexes: All the oxalate complexes were prepared by refluxing appropriate metaloxalate in an ethanolic solution of the ligand in 1 : 2 for 8 hr on steambath with continued stirring. Complexes thus obtained were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in an evacuated desiccator over $CaCl_2$.

Thiocyanato-bis(3-phenylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2) iron(II): Ethanolic soln of $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ was mixed with calculated amount of NH_4SCN to get solution of $Fe(SCN)_3$ which was refluxed with 2 fold excess of ligand for 4 hr. The volume was reduced under vacuum and red crystals of desired complex were filtered and dried.

Thiocyanato-bis(3-phenylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2) cobalt(II): On reaction with NH_4SCN (0.04 mole), the ethanolic solution of $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.02 mole) yielded a dark blue solution. This solution when refluxed with ethanolic solution of ligand (PAB) yielded rose-red crystals of the desired complex. The complex was filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Thiocyanato-bis(3-phenylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2) nickel(II): A cold ethanolic solution of $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.01 mole) was treated with $KSCN$ (0.02 mole). The resulting solid KNO_3 was filtered and rejected. Treatment of the filtrate with ethanolic solution of ligand yielded violet coloured crystalline compound which was washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under vacuum.

(b) *Pharmacological*: Details of method employed for pharmacological screening of these complexes have been published in earlier publications⁴⁻⁶.

(c) *Microbiological* :

(i) *Amoebicidal activity* : This activity against *Entamoeba histolytica* was evaluated by the method of Das *et al.*^{12,13}. 0.2 ml inoculum containing about 2500 amoebae was put into cavity slide filled with 0.8 ml fresh medium having requisite drug concentration, the cavity was covered, sealed with paraffin wax and put in moist chamber at 37°. Mortality was observed after 18, 24 and 48 hr under inverted microscope. No drug was employed in control. Flagyl (1 µg/ml) was taken as reference standard. Amoebicidal end points of various complexes are listed in Table 3.

(ii) *Antibacterial activity* : Agar diffusion¹⁴ technique was employed for assessing bactericidal activity of these complexes against *Staphylococcus aureus* (obtained from Public Analyst Laboratory, U.P., Lucknow). Sterile filter paper (Whatman No. 41) discs of 5 mm diameter saturated with soln of test compound (10 µg/ml) were kept on nutrient agar plates (1.5% w/v agar; 0.5% w/v glucose and 2.5% w/v peptone at pH 6.8-7.0) after drying up the solvent. The plates were incubated at 37° for 24 hr and zones of inhibition based upon zone size (- = no inhibition, + = zone size 6.8 mm, ++ = zone size 8-12 mm, +++ = zone size 12-20 mm, ++++ = zone size > 20 mm) around the disc were measured. Observations were taken as mean of duplicate experiments and bio-assay data are recorded in Table 3.

(iii) *Antifungal activity* : Fungitoxicity was evaluated against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Fusarium solani* by agar plate technique¹⁵ at three concentrations viz., 1:1000, 1:10000 and 1:100000. Every experiment was performed in triplicate and the average percentage inhibition was calculated. The results of fungitoxicity are tabulated in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analytical data (Table 1) complexes have been formulated as MX_2L_3 where M = Fe(II), Co(II) or Ni(II); X = 0.5 $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ or SCN^- ; L = 3-phenylaminomethylbenzoxazolinone-2. The molar conductances of all the complexes are less than 1.0 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$ indicating that they are non-electrolytes.

A considerable negative shift in the NH stretching frequency in the complexes as compared to the ligand (at 3375 cm^{-1}) indicates the coordination of ligand through nitrogen. It has been observed that in all thiocyanate complexes C=O frequency of ligand suffered a negative shift, which indicates the involvement of ketonic oxygen in complexation. The C=O frequency of ligand interferes with the ir absorption bands of oxalate; so it was not possible to identify ligands C=O frequency separately in these complexes.

The important infrared assignments in the oxalate complexes are of carboxylate ion. It gives

two absorption bands of high intensity at 1670 and 1650 cm^{-1} which are associated with asymmetric C=O stretchings and one weak symmetric band at 1400 cm^{-1} . On coordination, asymmetric bands undergo positive shift while symmetric band is shifted to lower frequency side. The same has been found true in all oxalate complexes.

The thiocyanate complexes show bands at 805 cm^{-1} and 482 cm^{-1} , the regions of $\nu\text{C-S}$ and δNCS vibrations respectively. A band around 800 cm^{-1} in thiocyanate complexes can be assigned to the $\nu\text{C-S}$ stretching mode of N-bonded thiocyanate⁹.

Electronic and magnetic data :

Iron(2+) complexes : A shoulder at 370 nm in the spectrum of iron(II) complexes is attributed to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The band at 555 nm with a shoulder around 495 nm is assigned to $T_{2g} \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition which is responsible for intense colour of iron(24) complexes. D_q value of about 924 cm^{-1} calculated from the maximum of the major (d-d) band suggests octahedral structures for these complexes.

Cobalt(2+) complexes : Bands at 1050 and 482 nm are assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. The energy of ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(F)$ transition has been calculated to be 22886 cm^{-1} (441 nm)¹⁰. The spectrochemical parameters of this complex, $Dq = 838.28 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\beta = 0.78$, $B' = 873.2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and magnetic moment of 4.97 B.M. confirm its octahedral structure.

Nickel(2+) complexes : The electronic spectral bands at 30310 cm^{-1} , 17850 cm^{-1} and 10750 cm^{-1} are due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ transitions. All these transitions are spin allowed transitions and are designated as V_3 , V_2 and V_1 respectively. The ratio of V_2/V_1 (17850/10750) comes out to be 1.66 which suggests octahedral geometry to these complexes. Values of various ligand field parameters viz. Dq (1075 cm^{-1}), B' (1060 cm^{-1}) and β (0.98) further substantiate the above conclusion. The magnetic moments of 3.10 and 3.25 B.M. for both the complexes of nickel also confirm the assigned geometry.

LD_{50} (the measure of toxicity) values of the complexes indicate that toxicity decreases with increasing size of the metal ion i.e. iron(2+) complexes are least toxic. In order to evaluate the effects on CNS, the compounds (at 1/5 LD_{50} to dose) were administered intraperitoneally to groups of 5 albino mice and they were continuously observed for 2 hr and then at two hourly intervals for the next 6 hr. All complexes stimulated CNS as a result of which spontaneous motor activity (SMA) and reactivity increased. None of the iron complexes showed any toxic effect whereas other complexes of this series exhibited a number of toxic effects e.g. ataxia, tremor piloerection and dragging in increasing order $\text{Fe} < \text{Co} < \text{Ni} < \text{Cu}$.

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL DATA*

Compound	Colour	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	IR spectral bands (cm^{-1})				Diffuse reflectance bands λ_{max} (nm)
			NH	MN	MO	CS	
$\text{Fe}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$	Dark red	5.60	3280s	238m	383m	—	240, 280, 370, 494, 555, 600, 950, 1180
$\text{Fe}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Dark red	5.50	3260s	229m	350m	790s	250, 295, 370, 495, 555, 960, 1240
$\text{Co}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$	Pink	4.97	3278s	512m	460m, 430m	—	230, 275, 305, 482, 572, 620, 1050, 1391
$\text{Co}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Rose red	5.06	3260s	500m	460m, 433m	805s	245, 295, 330, 482, 618, 1050, 1220, 1387
$\text{Ni}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$	Green	3.25	3296s	415m	365m	—	220, 245, 278, 330, 360, 560, 655, 928, 1350
$\text{Ni}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Violet	3.10	3265s	432m	350m	800s	230, 245, 330, 390, 560, 660, 930, 1300

Note—Values observed for C, H and N are in good agreement with calculated values.

* For chemistry of Cu^{2+} complexes see reference No. 3.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING

Sl. No.	Compound	Approximate LD_{50} mg/kg i.p. (mice)	Effect on CNS (mice) at 1/5 LD_{50}	Effect on OVS (cat) at 2.5 mg/kg iv, mm Hg/minutes	A.I.A. (mice) % inhibition at 1/5 LD_{50} (oral)	Anti-PCA (mice) % inhibition at 1/5 LD_{50} (oral)	Diuresis (Rat) at 1/4 LD_{50}
1.	$\text{Fe}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$	800	Increased SMA, reactivity and resp.	15/25	—	55	30
2.	$\text{Fe}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	681	—do—	2/30	34	58	30
3.	$\text{Co}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$	480	Increased SMA, reactivity and resp. straubtail	35/30	20	45	14
4.	$\text{Co}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	350	Increased SMA, reactivity and resp. ataxia	35/40	18	45	12
5.	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$	200	Increased SMA, reactivity, ataxia, tremor and bilorection	40/30	—	60	—
6.	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	150	—do—	50/30	—	66	—
7.	$\text{Cu}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)$	75	Increased SMA followed by sudden decrease in SMA and resp. dragging piloerection	50/30	10	70	—
8.	$\text{Cu}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	75	—do—	56/45	8	78	—
9.	PAB	681	—	—	16	30	23

TABLE 3—RESULTS OF MICROBIOLOGICAL SCREENING

Sl. No.	Compound	Amoebicidal end-point against <i>E. histolytica</i> ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Antibacterial activity (<i>S. aureus</i>)	Antifungal activity, average % inhibition after 7 days			
				Conc.	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>E. solani</i>
1.	$\text{Fe}(\text{PAB})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	Not active	—	1 : 1000	38.0	46.7	45.0
				1 : 10000	30.6	30.5	32.0
				1 : 100000	20.0	15.0	28.4
2.	$\text{Fe}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	500	—	1 : 1000	35.2	38.0	36.8
				1 : 10000	28.0	26.5	28.5
				1 : 100000	15.6	15.0	16.0
3.	$\text{Co}(\text{PAB})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	Not active	—	1 : 1000	48.5	50.0	48.5
				1 : 10000	32.0	43.6	35.2
				1 : 100000	28.5	30.5	24.8
4.	$\text{Co}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	250	++	1 : 1000	45.0	47.2	42.8
				1 : 10000	32.6	35.0	36.7
				1 : 100000	25.0	26.5	25.0
5.	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAB})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	500	++	1 : 1000	74.0	72.6	70.8
				1 : 10000	68.5	65.0	65.6
				1 : 100000	56.5	58.0	56.0
6.	$\text{Ni}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	125	++++	1 : 1000	68.7	60.5	60.8
				1 : 10000	52.5	50.0	52.8
				1 : 100000	45.0	30.8	40.6
7.	$\text{Cu}(\text{PAB})_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$	250	+++	1 : 1000	90.0	88.0	75.0
				1 : 10000	82.8	76.0	70.2
				1 : 100000	70.6	60.0	56.3
8.	$\text{Cu}(\text{PAB})_2(\text{SCN})_2$	62.5	++++	1 : 1000	80.6	70.8	70.0
				1 : 10000	68.0	58.6	60.6
				1 : 100000	56.2	45.0	48.0
9.	PAB	Not active	++	1 : 1000	32.6	28.5	37.6
				1 : 10000	27.8	12.0	20.5
				1 : 100000	15.0	5.0	12.8

These toxic effects further confirm the above view of increasing toxicity with decrease in metal ion size. However, in both the copper complexes stimulation of CNS was followed by depression (i.e. decreased SMA and reactivity) and it was due to super toxicity of copper complexes ($LD_{50}=75$ mg/kg). The increased rate of respiration was due to direct stimulation of respiratory centre and dilation of bronchioles.

All the complexes produced hypotension ranging from 15-56 mm of mercury for 25-45 min. These results as well as results of our earlier investigations^{4,6} reveal that metallic part of the complexes is responsible for hypotension and in fact all metal complexes produced hypotension independent of coordination number and geometry. The degree and duration of hypotension have been found to be increased with decreasing size of the metal cation and actually all the copper complexes of this series produced significant hypotension, for more than half an hour. However, the ligand (PAB), when given alone did not show any sign of activity on CNS or CVS. Some of the complexes and ligand itself exhibited weak anti-inflammatory activity and diuresis.

All these complexes, when subjected to anti-anaphylactic testing produced significant inhibition. It has also been noticed that all the complexes exhibited greater inhibition as compared to the ligand. $Cu(PAB)_2(SCN)_2$ was found to be most active against passive cutaneous anaphylaxis followed by $Cu(PAB)_2C_2O_4$ and merits detailed pharmacological, biochemical and histopathological investigations. Anti-anaphylactic activity of the complexes may be either due to their preventive action on the release of histamine from the site of intradermal injection or by antagonising the action of the released histamine on the capillaries of the affected areas⁶.

$Fe(2+)$ and $Co(2+)$ oxalate complexes of PAB are inactive against *E. histolytica* whereas $Ni(2+)$ and $Cu(2+)$ oxalate complexes are active only at higher concentrations. On the other hand all thiocyanate complexes are active and activity increases in the order $Fe < Co < Ni < Cu$. These results indicate that not only the cation but also the anion is equally responsible for the amoebicidal activity. If we consider oxalate or thiocyanate complexes separately it becomes clear that amoebicidal activity increases as the radius of the metal ion decreases. Further, the activity is potentiated if oxalate is replaced by thiocyanate. These two effects when combined together, produced most active complex $[Cu(PAB)_2(SCN)_2]$ of this series.

However, PAB itself was found to be completely inactive against *E. histolytica*, which clearly indicates that coordination complexes may have more pronounced destructive effect on microorganism than their parent constituents.

First three complexes of Table 3 do not exert any destructive action against *S. aureus*, whereas compounds No. 4 and 5 rendered weak inhibition similar to PAB. However, compounds No. 6 and 8 produced significant inhibition followed by compound No. 7. These results confirm the views of Weinberg¹⁶.

Similar to the findings of Srivastava¹⁷ we observed here that fungitoxicity increases with decreasing radius of the metal ion and in fact copper complexes of this series exhibited pronounced antifungal activity against *A. niger*, *A. flavus* and *F. solani*. We also noticed that the complexes are more fungitoxic than ligand itself.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Director, C. D. R. I., Lucknow, Prof. J. N. Rai, Botany Department, Lucknow University, and Public Analyst to the Government of U. P. for their help. Financial support of C. S. I. R., New Delhi is also gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. S. K. BAJPAI and P. R. SHUKLA, *Z. Analyt. Chem.*, 1976, 280, 361.
2. S. K. BAJPAI and J. P. PANDEV, *Z. Analyt. Chem.*, 1977, 287, 312.
3. S. K. BAJPAI and D. PRAKASH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1979, 41, 756.
4. S. K. BAJPAI and P. R. SHUKLA, *Ind. J. Pharm.*, 1975, 7, 21.
5. S. K. BAJPAI, K. KAR and B. N. DEHAWAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1978, 47, 406.
6. S. K. BAJPAI and P. R. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 219.
7. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Soc.*, 1968, 59, 39.
8. N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4109.
9. M. E. FARAGO and J. M. JAMES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1706.
10. A. M. SPECA, L. L. PYTLEWSKI and N. M. KARAYANNIS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 36, 1227.
11. L. SACCONI, *Trans. Metal Chem.*, 1968, 4, 199.
12. S. R. DAS, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, 44, 463.
13. S. R. DAS and B. N. PRASAD, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, 48, 69.
14. R. S. VARMA and W. L. NOBLES, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1973, 61, 112.
15. J. G. HORSFALL, *Bot. Rev.*, 1945, 5, 357.
16. E. WEINBERG, *Bact. Rev.*, 1957, 21, 46.
17. R. SRIVASTAVA, *I.org. Chim. Acta*, 1980, B6, L48.